

What are the concerns around plastics and why do we need to regulate them?

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Note:

Twenty years ago, exempting polymers from the registration requirement under REACH was a political compromise. As part of its 2020 Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), the European Commission has also announced a comprehensive revision of the REACH Regulation. Among other things, the registration requirement is to be extended in future to certain polymers of concern (PoC). The criteria for classification as PoC are currently still under discussion.

At the Regulatory Developments @ Regulatory Summit Europe 2026 on April 20 in Brussels, Prof. Dr. Uwe Lahl will give a presentation on the topic of "What are the concerns around plastics and why do we need to regulate them?" In view of the topicality of this issue and the upcoming discussions at EU level, we prepared this background paper for all interested parties.

Abbreviations

CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging (of Chemicals)
CoRAP	ECHA's Community Rolling Action Plan
CSS	Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability
Da	Dalton (1 Da = one twelfth of the mass of the carbon isotope ¹² C)
DPP	Digital Product Passport
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EEA	European Economic Area
EINECS	European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances
ELINCS	European List of Notified Chemical Substances
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
FCA	Food-contact articles
FCM	Food contact materials
IECSC	Inventory of Existing Chemical Substances manufactured or imported in China
Mg	Megagram, formerly "ton" (1000 Kilogram)
MOCS	More than One Constituent Substance
NIAS	non-intentionally added substances
NLP	No-Longer Polymers
PE	Polyethylene
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PFCAs	Perfluorocarboxylic acids
PFHxA	Perfluorohexanoic acid
PFHxS	Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFOS	Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid
PLC	Polymers of Low Concern
POP	Persistent Organic Pollutant
PP	Polypropylene
PRR	Polymers requiring registration
PS	Polystyrene
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
RAC	ECHAS's Risk Assessment Committee
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
SEAC	ECHA's Socio-Economic Analysis Committee
SVHC	Substance(s) of very high Concern
vP	very persistent

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1. Background

Macromolecules (synonymous: polymers) are defined as molecules of high relative molecular mass, the structure of which essentially comprises the multiple repetition of units derived, actually or conceptually, from molecules of low relative molecular mass [1]. Chemically, they are formed from smaller units (monomer molecules). A monomer is defined as a molecule which can undergo polymerisation thereby contributing constitutional units to the essential structure of a macromolecule. Oligomers are molecules that consist of a small plurality of units (monomers) [2]. They are referred to as dimers (2 units), trimers (3), tetramers (4) and so on, up to a few tens; the upper limit is not clearly defined. "Polymerisation" is a generic term for the process of converting a mixture of monomers into a polymer [3]; the main reaction types are polycondensation, polyaddition and radical polymerisation¹.

The degree of polymerisation ranges from three over several tens (oligomers) or several hundreds to several ten-thousands monomers (polymers). Commercially available polymers do not have a uniform degree of polymerisation. Strictly speaking, therefore, it is not possible to refer to them as a single substance². As a rule, in the case of so-called mono- or multi-constituent substances, it is assumed that the (hazardous) properties of a substance originate from its main constituent or constituents.

The term **More than One Constituent Substance** (MOCS) has been introduced by revision of the CLP directive [4] as an auxiliary³ term to describe substances in which certain (hazardous) properties do not originate solely from the main component(s), but also from additives, impurities or other components [5]. For example, in the production of polymers, additives are added intentionally, e.g. to protect the polymer (stabilisers) or to support polymerisation, to initiate polymerisation and/or control the formation of the macromolecular structure ('aid to polymerisation' [6, Article 3 (10)], and which are inseparable from the polymer. These stabilisers belong to the "basic equipment of the substance" [7]. In contrast, non-intentionally added substances' (NIAS) are "an impurity in the substances used or a reaction intermediate formed during the production process or a decomposition or reaction product" [6, Article 3 (9)]. The kind of impurities is often unknown [8].

The distinctive feature of polymers from a substance regulation perspective is that we must not only assess a mixture of polymers with varying degrees of polymerisation, but also the continuous – and in some cases dramatic – changes in this mixture, as polymers age or degrade due to various influences. A scientifically comprehensive assessment would therefore need to take these change processes into account. This also means that the changes can be traced back to the level of the monomers. Traces of monomers can already be detected in freshly produced polymers. These concentrations can increase drastically as the material ages. We will refer to all of these collectively as "polymers" in the following.

¹ In addition, there is also cationic, anionic and coordinative polymerisation.

² Substance "means a chemical element and its compounds in the natural state or obtained by any manufacturing process, including any additive necessary to preserve its stability and any impurity deriving from the process used, but excluding any solvent which may be separated without affecting the stability of the substance or changing its composition". <https://reachonline.eu/reach/en/title-i-chapter-2-article-3.html>

³ MOCS as an auxiliary term is neither a new type of substance nor does it represent a new substance definition. <https://doi.org/10.21934/helpdeskfokus:clp20250805>

Plastics are compounds of one type or different types of polymers (precisely: polymeric MOCS) and at least one not related substance, typically referred to as **additive**. An additive is defined as "a substance which is intentionally added to plastics to achieve a physical or chemical effect during processing of the plastic or in the final material or article; it is intended to be present in the final material or article" [6, Article 3 (7)]. There are several thousand additives for polymer compounding [9]. Without additives more or less all polymers cannot be used to manufacture plastics [10,11,12].

Figure 1 provides an overview of the basic composition of plastics: polymers (polymeric MOCS) and additives (non-exhaustive list). More details on additives are given in section 3.

Figure 1: Polymers (highlighted in yellow) and plastics © BZL GmbH

Plastic compounds are used as a main structural component⁴ of a variety of final materials, articles⁵ or products⁶ – depending on the area of law (REACH/substance law or product law, e.g. for toys), used synonymously here. The regulatory requirements described in this paper are based on polymers but also on (plastic) articles or products.

⁴ 'Plastic' is defined as "polymer to which additives or other substances may have been added, which is capable of functioning as a main structural component of final materials and articles" [Article 3 (2)].

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32011R0010>

⁵ 'Article' is defined in REACH as an object which, during production, is given a specific shape, surface, or design that determines its function to a greater degree than does its chemical composition. Example is an egg spoon.

⁶ The term 'product' is not defined in REACH. As we make regulatory proposals that also affect product law, we also use this term. A complex **product** can be made up of **different articles**. Example is a Barbie doll. Today, its head is made from a vinyl compound, its arms from EVA (ethylene-vinyl acetate), its torso from ABS (acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene) and its legs from polypropylene and PVC. <https://www.coda-plastics.co.uk/blog/life-in-plastic-how-mattel-created-its-new-diverse-line-of-barbie-dolls/>

The REACH regulation (**R**egistration, **E**valuation, **A**uthorisation and **R**estriction of Chemicals) [13] has now been in force for around 20 years and has brought both successes and failures and shows optimisation potential (e.g. [14,15,16]). Perhaps the most significant achievement of REACH was the mandatory registration of all relevant chemicals with the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). Polymers are exempt from this registration requirement (see section 2). Various parties have called for improvements to the REACH regulation (e.g. in terms of efficiency) [17,18,19,20,21]. The EU Commission has announced an amendment. In 2020, the EU Commission announced in its Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) [22] – published as part of the European Green Deal – to extend the duty of registration under REACH to certain "polymers of concern". Various preliminary studies have already been conducted on the question of which and how polymers should be subject to mandatory registration [23,24,25].

It is now unclear whether the Commission will present a modernisation proposal. The Commission has repeatedly missed the deadlines it set for presenting its proposal. Politically, this amendment comes at a time when the European economy is struggling and the chemical industry in particular is complaining about excessive burdens in the EU, which are hampering its international competitiveness.

2. Are polymers not covered by REACH?

The REACH regulation serves in particular to register the many chemicals that have been on the market for decades (so-called existing substances). Today, without registration, a substance may not be marketed (production, import) in the European Economic Area (EEA⁷). However, substances that are only marketed in small quantities (< 1 Megagram (Mg)⁸ per year (1 Mg/a) per company are exempt from the registration requirement.

Substance regulation under REACH generally begins with the notification of a substance by the manufacturer or importer of that chemical. He/she must check with ECHA whether a valid registration has already been submitted for the same substance. If not, the registrant has to submit a comprehensive substance dossier, which allows the registrant to evaluate the hazardousness of a substance and the risks associated with its uses. Once this dossier is formally complete (and the registration fee has been paid), ECHA assigns a registration number to the substance in question, and the substance is therefore registered under REACH. If necessary, an evaluation by ECHA or by the competent authorities of the Member States follows and – depending on the evaluation and based on a transparent, clearly structured procedure – authorisation, restriction or banning can follow.

Polymers as a group are, as said, exempted from the registration requirement under REACH. This means that registration dossiers with the results of routine tests are not required and

⁷ REACH directly applies in all 27 Member States of the European Union plus Northern Ireland and through national regulations in the EFTA-EEA States Iceland (Regulation No 888/2015), Liechtenstein (Decision No 25/2008 of the EEA Joint Committee) and Norway (FOR-2008-05-30-516).

⁸ 1 Megagram = 1000 kilogram, formerly known as "ton"

the subsequent evaluations⁹ do not happen¹⁰. What is the background for this exemption from the registration requirement? To answer this, we need to take a look back, because the exemption was a political decision. Table 1 gives a survey on 60 years of chemicals regulation in Europe with a particular focus on how polymers have been regulated in the past.

Table 1: Milestones – 60 years of chemicals regulation in Europe (focus on polymers)

Entry in force / Transposition in national law	Regulation	Relevant aspects
29.06.1967 (date of notification) / 01.02.1972 (valid until 31.05.2015) ¹¹	Council Directive 67/548/EEC of 27 June 1967 ... the classification, packaging and labelling of dangerous substances [26]	" Dangerous substances Directive ": <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Required suppliers to classify, label and package dangerous substances according to harmonised rules.
19.09.1979 / 18.09.1981 (valid until 31.05.2015) ¹²	Council Directive 79/831/EEC of 18 September 1979 amending for the sixth time Directive 67/548/EEC ... [27]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First distinction between new substances and existing substances by introduction of EINECS (European Inventory of Existing Chemical Substances) – the "existing substances register". "This inventory contains the definitive list of all substances deemed to be on the Community market on 18 September 1981. New substances have to be registered if they are placed on the market in quantities of 1 Mg or more per year. Applies to monomers, too. Polymers shall be considered as having been notified ..., except those containing in combined form 2% or more of any monomer unmarketed before 18/09/1981 (= two years after entry in force).
15.06.1990 (date of publication)	EINECS (Council Directive 79/831/EEC)	Final version published in the Official Journal of the EU: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100,106 substances listed in EINECS; number of existing substances marketed in volumes >1 Mg/a is estimated at 30,000 [28]
15.01.1991 (six months after publication)	EINECS (Council Directive 79/831/EEC)	Any substance on the Community market, either on its own or in a preparation, must either be on the inventory or notified in accordance with the requirements of the Directive.
22.05.1992 / 31.10.1993 (valid until 31.05.2015) ¹³	Council Directive 92/32/EEC of 30 April 1992 amending for the seventh time Directive 67/548/EEC ... [29]	The substances listed below shall be considered as having been notified within the meaning of this Directive when the following conditions are fulfilled: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> polymers, with the exception of those which contain in combined form 2% or more of any substance which is not on EINECS, ... substances placed on the market in quantities of less than 10 kg per year per manufacturer ...

⁹ According to legal requirements, ECHA is obliged to check at least 5% of registration dossiers per tonnage level for quality.

¹⁰ Besides the evaluation based on a registration dossier (Section VI REACH Regulation), substance evaluation is envisaged if, beyond the testing and information requirements within the scope of registration, there are justified assumptions of risk to humans and the environment. This evaluation is carried out by the Member States, which have twelve months to clarify the potential risks of a substance.

¹¹ All dates: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/DE/ALL/?uri=celex:31967L0548>

¹² All dates: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:31979L0831&qid=1773048414185>

¹³ All dates: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/de/ALL/?uri=CELEX:31992L0032>

Entry in force / Transposition in national law	Regulation	Relevant aspects
		Article 12 – Polymers For polymers, the specific provisions concerning the technical dossiers contained in the notifications and referred to in Articles 7 (1) and 8 (1) shall be laid down in Annex VII, in the form of Annex VII.D , in accordance with the procedure referred to in Article 29 (4) (b).
04.06.1993 / - (valid until 31.05.2008) ¹⁴	Council Regulation (EEC) No 793/93 of 23 March 1993 on ... existing substances [30]	"Existing Substances Regulation": <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry must submit relevant data and information for all market-relevant existing substances with an annual tonnage of 10 Mg or more.
03.12.1993 / 31.12.1993 (valid until 31.05.2008) ¹⁵	Commission Directive 93/105/EC of 25 November 1993 laying down Annex VII D, ... referred to in Article 12 of the seventh Amendment of Council Directive 67/548 /EEC [31]	Annex VII D Specific provisions concerning the technical dossier ("Base Set") contained in the notifications <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The requirements regarding the scope of data to be provided vary depending on the suspected level of hazard. "Substances with a high number-average molecular weight, a low content of low molecular weight species and a low solubility/extractivity will be regarded as being non-bioavailable. Consequently, the following criteria shall be used to determine the polymers for which a reduced test package is acceptable ..." "To avoid unnecessary testing, the grouping of polymers into families shall be possible."
27.02.2001 (date of presentation)	White Paper – Strategy for a future Chemicals Policy [28]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some 2700 new substances registered. Some 140 of the existing 100,106 substances have been identified as priority substances and are subject to comprehensive risk assessment carried out by Member State authorities.
01.06.2007	Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) , establishing a European Chemicals Agency , ... [32]	"REACH": <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In accordance with the principle of "no data, no market", from then on, chemical substances can only be manufactured and placed on the market/imported in quantities of 1 Mg per year or more per company if they have been registered beforehand. For a transitional period, it is possible to register existing substances ("phase-in substances") that are manufactured or imported in quantities of 1 Mg per year or more per company in three time periods (see below). <p>By the time REACH came into force,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> approximately 10,000 dossiers had been submitted for almost 5300 new substances, and only 141 substances had been evaluated systematically [33].

¹⁴ All dates: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:31993R0793&qid=1773053436050>

¹⁵ All dates: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:31993L0105&qid=1776416777607>

Entry in force / Transposition in national law	Regulation	Relevant aspects
20.01.2009	Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures [34]	<p>"CLP regulation": Suppliers of substances and mixtures must classify these before placing them on the market, whether they consist of substances (including polymers):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for which classification is harmonised and as such is obligatory for suppliers (see Annex VI of the CLP Regulation) or, • that suppliers must self-classify in relation to specific criteria, consisting of the 15 hazard categories defined in the directive (see 67/548/EEC) or the 28 hazard classes which replaced them in the CLP Regulation. <p><i>Since 01.12.2010 and until 01.06.2015, substances had to be classified according to both the DSD and the CLP Regulation.</i></p>
30.11.2010 (deadline)	Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006	<p>REACH: End of registration phase 1 for "phase-in substances"</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • annual tonnage of 1000 Mg or more • all CMR substances in quantities of 1 Mg or more per year per company • environmentally hazardous substances in annual tonnages of 100 Mg or more per company <p>Result: 20,000 registration dossiers for 3400 phase-in-substances [33]</p>
31.05.2013 (deadline)	Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006	<p>REACH: End of registration phase 2 for "phase-in substances":</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • annual tonnage of 100 Mg or more <p>Result: 9000 registration dossiers for 3000 phase-in-substances [33]</p>
31.05.2018 (deadline)	Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006	<p>REACH: End of registration phase 3 for "phase-in substances":</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • annual tonnage between 1 and 100 Mg <p>Result (estimated): around 60,000 registration dossiers for some 20,000 phase-in-substances [33]</p>

So, following Council Directive 79/831/EEC of September 18, 1979, polymers were considered as having been notified, "except those containing in combined form 2% or more of any **new monomer**"¹⁶. Existing monomers were registered in EINECS. With Council Directive 92/32/EEC of 30 April 1992, "polymers became notifiable substances if they contain 2% or more **new substances** (i.e., generally substances not listed in EINECS)" [35]. In addition, the **definition of polymers** was changed with the result that substances previously considered to be polymers were (in theory) no longer excluded from regulation. The **No-longer-Polymer (NLP)**¹⁷ list consists of such substances (former 'polymers') that were commercially available between 18.9.1981 and 31.10.1993. One could certainly argue whether NLP substances are really not polymers. However, an exemption from the

¹⁶ "Monomer unmarketed before 18/09/1981", i.e. two years after entry in force

¹⁷ The NLP list mainly consists of the following groups: alkoxyated substances, oligomeric reaction products, oligomers from one monomer only, dimers and trimers, polymer-like substances containing 50% or more by weight of species with the same molecular weight. https://www.cirs-reach.com/Inventory/EU_EINECS_ELINCS_NLP.html

notification requirement has also been established for NLP substances: "Any substance on this list or which is decided by a Competent Authority to meet the criteria is exempt from notification" [36].

As an interim conclusion, Table 1 shows that before REACH came into force, polymers were exempt from the notification/registration requirement. However, for new polymers, a notification requirement accompanied by comprehensive substance dossiers was imposed. This historically significant regulation was repealed when REACH came into force.

Leaving aside the special treatment for new polymers, unfortunately, the success of this Europe-wide regulation of existing substances has been very limited. Only 141 substances had been systematically evaluated under the Existing Substances Regulation before REACH came into force (01.06.2007). "The main burden fell on the national authorities, which carried out the risk assessments using industry data. Overall, the process led to very lengthy discussions with industrial companies, some of which acted according to the principle of 'no data, no problems'" [33].

All in all, then, from a historical perspective, this is a highly unsatisfactory situation, including with regard to non-polymers. This shortcoming should therefore be remedied by the new regulation. The process started at EU level in 1998 and culminated in the EU Commission's 2001 *White Paper* [28]. Major problems were identified, in particular a general lack of knowledge about the properties and the uses of existing substances and the fact that the existing substances, which amounted to more than 99% of the total volume of all substances on the market, were not subject to the same testing requirements as for new substances [28]. The EU Commission's 2001 *White Paper* was followed by a five-year "battle of lobbying" in Brussels and the member states [37]. Sharp "dispatches" have also been exchanged between the EU and the U.S. Germany played an important role in reaching a compromise which was prepared in the Chancellery in an informal working group between VCI (German Chemical Industry Association), BASF, IGBCE (Trade Union for mining, chemicals and energy industries), and ministries.

As part of the political compromise, it was decided to exempt polymers from registration requirement. Following a trilogue, REACH was finally formally adopted in the European Parliament on 13.12.2006 and in the Council on 18.12.2006. Entry into force was 01.06.2007.

One part of the REACH regulation was establishing a European Chemicals Agency (in Helsinki, Finland). On its founding in 2008, ECHA received the European Chemical inventory from the EU's Joint Research Centre (JRC), containing 106,212 unique substances/entries. The EC inventory before REACH comprised of three lists [38]:

- **European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS):** list of substances, excluding polymers, that were recorded as being commercially available in the EU from 1.1.1971 to 18.9.1981: "existing substances"
- **European List of Notified Chemical Substances (ELINCS):** hazardous substances, commercially available after 18.9.1981: "new substances"
- **No-Longer Polymers (NLP) list:** former 'polymers' that were commercially available between 18.9.1981 and 31.10.1993.

Table 2 from [39] shows the system used for assigning EC numbers before REACH.¹⁸

Table 2: European Chemical inventory before REACH [39]

EC no.	Status	List
2xx-xxx-x 3xx-xxx-x	Existing substances	EINECS (European IN ventory of Existing C ommercial chemical S ubstances) List
4xx-xxx-x	New substances	ELINCS (European L ist of N otified C hemical S ubstances) List
5xx-xxx-x	No-Longer Polymers	NLP (N o- L onger P olymers) List

These three lists have been incorporated into the REACH "**list of registered substances**" as follows:

- **New substances** notified up to 01.06.2008 were considered 'registered' and received a registration number by end of 2008.
- **Existing substances** that are manufactured or imported in quantities of 1 Mg per year or more per company could be registered in three time periods ("phase-in substances"): deadlines were, depending on the annual tonnage, 30.11.2010, 31.05.2013 and 31.05.2018.
- **NLPs** "shall be registered as a normal phase-in substance under REACH" [40].

Part of the compromise, as said, was to exempt polymers from the registration requirement. What were the main reasons for this special treatment? The first argument was such as in the time of EINECS: they are less hazardous because of the size of their molecules. A second argument was complexity and the concern of overloading the registration process at the start. But the "loss" of substance evaluations should be partially compensated with the registration requirement for unbound and bound monomers (see Art. 6(2) and (3) REACH Regulation and [41,42]).

Another part of the political compensation was the review clause in Article 138 (2), which allowed for the inclusion of polymers on a later occasion. The wording of the review clause is as follows (highlighted by the authors): "The Commission may present legislative proposals as soon as a practicable and cost-efficient way of **selecting polymers for registration** on the basis of sound technical and valid scientific criteria can be established, **and after publishing a report on the following**:

- (a) the **risks** posed by polymers in comparison with other substances;
- (b) the **need**, if any, to register certain types of polymer, taking account of competitiveness and innovation on the one hand and the **protection of human health and the environment** on the other."

¹⁸ The format of the list numbers will become alphanumeric. "It will keep the same length but begin with a letter as the first character. Once all letters have been used as the first character, the second character will become a letter, and so on.

Example of the current list number: 100-000-1

Example of the new list number: A00-001-5

List numbers assigned before the format change will stay as they are and will not be affected by the new format."
<https://echa.europa.eu/de/about-ec-and-list-numbers>

REACH has led to a significant reduction in the number of registered substances compared with the substances notified 20 years ago. While the number of notified substances before REACH came into force was a good 106,000, the current REACH registration list contains "only" just under 23,300 (see Table 3). It can be assumed that this reduction is also due to the fact that many of the at that time existing substances were not/are today not available on the market or are only used to a limited extent (less than 1 Mg/a per company). However, it cannot be ruled out, particularly for imports, that there is a high number of unreported cases of substances on the market that are not registered. And since polymers are exempt from the registration requirement under REACH, it is not surprising that only a small selection of polymers is represented in the ECHA CHEM¹⁹ database. A search for "polymer" (02.03.2026) yielded 54 existing (EINECS) and 75 new (ELINCS) substances, with 24 of the latter without a Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS) Registry Number. The existing substances here comprised monomers/oligomers²⁰ and others. We haven't checked how many of these substances are still active, i.e., are currently still being manufactured or imported within the European Economic Area (EEA).

3. What about the additives?

The exemption of polymers from the registration requirement, coupled with the simultaneous exemption of certain additives, has in our view contributed to the emergence of a "grey area" in this regard, and it is likely that there is a high number of unreported substances that are introduced into our environment via plastic products.

A recently completed EU project (PlastChem [9]) investigated which additives and other chemicals can be found in plastics. Figure 2 shows that we can assume there are thousands of additives. Plastics used for food contact materials (FCM) and food-contact articles (FCA) have been particularly well researched. In addition to additives, 'non-intentionally added substances' (NIAS) must also be taken into account here. Of the approximately 14,000 substances, 1800 have been identified in the literature as being present in FCM. Of these 1800, it is known that they migrate from packaging, and a hazard has been determined for 388 of these substances [43].

¹⁹ <https://chem.echa.europa.eu/>

²⁰ e.g. acrylonitrile, buta-1,3-diene, ethylene, ethylene oxide, propene, styrene or vinyl acetate, petroleum fractions (e.g. hydrocarbons, C12-30, olefin-rich, ethylene polymerised by-product; distillates (petroleum), cracked steam-cracked petroleum distillates; distillates (petroleum), light catalytic cracked)

Figure 2: Overview of the functions of plastic additives and other chemicals (own graphic, according to [9])

How were these thousands of additives or NIAS been handled within the REACH registration process? Of course, these substances occur in very different concentrations. Stabilisers are important in terms of quantity. The European Chemicals Agency has made a decision on this [7] (highlighted by the authors): "A polymer, as any other substance ..., can also contain additives necessary to preserve the stability of the polymer **These stabilisers ... are considered to be part of the substance and do not have to be registered separately.** Stabilisers include, for example, heat stabilisers, anti-oxidants (both useful during extrusion) and light stabilisers (e.g. for preservation during use)." However, if stabilisers are used for other purposes, they are subject to registration, just like the other additives. The preconditions for additives are the same as for monomers (2% w/w in the polymer and >1 Mg/a)²¹. As stabilisers that solely are used to stabilise the polymer do not have to be registered, it is not known which chemicals are used in polymers and in what concentrations.

²¹ "The manufacturer or importer of a polymer must register the monomer substance(s) or other substance(s) that have not yet been registered by an upstream actor in the supply chain. The prerequisite is that they are present in a proportion of at least 2% by weight (w/w) in the polymer and that the total quantity of this monomer/other substance reaches or exceeds 1 Mg per year." (<https://www.reach-clp-biozid-helpdesk.de/DE/REACH/FAQ/Polymere>, translation by the authors)

Nevertheless, some stabilisers and antioxidants are registered with ECHA, as the plastic additives initiative [44] showed²². The referring "mapping exercise" by ECHA and 21 industry sector organisations (2016–2018) generated an overview of over 400 additives in plastics used in high volumes in the EU [45]: "The mapping considered substances registered under REACH at above 100 tonnes per year, and focused on plasticisers, flame retardants, pigments, antioxidants, antistatic agents, nucleating agents and various types of stabilisers." In sum, stabilisers and antioxidants amounted to 91 substances, 76 of them existing and nine new substances. Four of the stabilisers have no CAS number; three of them are reaction products/masses, for the fourth the substance name is not available.

Among these stabilisers, there are legacy substances²³ [11,12] like, e.g., the ultraviolet filter UV-328, a benzotriazole (2-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-ditertpentylphenol, EC-No. 247-384-8, CAS-No. 25973-55-1). UV-328 had already been placed on the SVHC candidate list in the EU in 2014 and was added to Annex XIV in 2018. The placing on the market and use of UV-328 without prior authorisation was prohibited in the EU from 27.11.2023 [46]. In May 2023, UV-328 has been added to Annex A of the Stockholm Convention with entry into force on 26.02.2025, but allowing any Party making use of the specific exemptions under certain conditions [47]. In July 2025, the European Commission published a Delegated Regulation, entering into force on 05.08.2025, granting exemptions for the placing on the market and the use of selected articles containing UV-328 until 2030 or (for selected spare parts) until 2043, [48]. No exceptions are provided for plastic products.

So, some progress is being made in the registration of plastic additives under REACH. And evaluation continues. ECHA has announced that it will be scrutinising further additives for SVHC classification in the coming years (including UV-326, UV-329 and triphenyl phosphate [49]). However, the overview in Figure 2 and the literature on FCM shows that ECHA's evaluation rate is too slow compared with the estimated number of substances. We will therefore in the following address the question of how further progress can be made in the evaluation of substances, but also in relation to consumer protection and product law.

4. REACH is already being used to regulate polymers

In addition to registration, REACH provides as mentioned other instruments to deal with hazardous substances and applications (evaluation, authorisation, restriction). These instruments can be used also for polymers, regardless of the lack of registration requirement. Here are two examples, where this has been applied in the past.

PFAS (Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances) is a collective term for multi-fluorinated compounds, including perfluorinated and polyfluorinated polymers.²⁴ The group comprises a total of over 10,000 individual compounds. Selected PFAS sub-groups are already subject to

²² This is also due to the vagueness of the ECHA recommendation. If stabilisers are not classified as part of the MOCS (**m**ore than **o**ne constituent substance), they are additives that would need to be registered.

²³ The term 'legacy substances' refers to substances whose use is now restricted or prohibited, but which are reintroduced into products via recycling from waste streams.

²⁴ We are using the ECHA's terminology here:

https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/17233/rest_pfas_bd_draft_240625_en.pdf

decisions of the Stockholm Convention and restrictions under REACH: PFOA [50,51], PFOS [52,53,54], PFHxS [55], PFHxA [56], and long-chain PFCAs [57,58]. Due to their persistence in the environment, which is likely to last for centuries, the EU is preparing a PFAS ban. Detailed legal analysis has shown that a restriction procedure with clear substitution requirements under REACH Annex XV is the most promising approach [59]. The procedure is underway. End of march 2026, ECHA declared that its "Risk Assessment Committee (RAC), in its final opinion, and its Socio-Economic Analysis Committee (SEAC), in its draft opinion, support an EU-wide restriction, subject to specific derogations, on the manufacture, placing on the market and use of PFAS. The Committees also recommend that any restriction should be complemented by effective measures to minimise emissions. The scientific conclusions of RAC and the draft opinion of SEAC mark a major step toward EU-level measures on PFAS" [60]. A final decision by the Commission is expected in 2027.

The polymer **PVC** has been the subject of debate for decades. In 2023, ECHA (at the request of the Commission) published its investigation report on PVC and PVC additives [61]. Conclusion by ECHA: regulatory measures are necessary to combat the risks posed by PVC and some of its additives: "Restriction under REACH is a regulatory instrument that would enable substitution of specific PVC additive groups in all relevant uses of PVC across several sectors." Next step: The Commission must mandate ECHA to prepare a REACH restriction proposal for PVC and its additives.

As an interim conclusion, it can therefore be stated that REACH would be a suitable and flexible legal instrument for regulating hazardous polymers, provided that a registration requirement, once introduced, were to highlight the need for action.

5. What additional effects could a registration requirement for polymers have?

So, if REACH is already being used for important regulatory tasks today, what additional benefits would a registration requirement for polymers bring? We will address this question in this chapter.

5.1. No system overload

In the past there was a risk that the registration requirement failed due to the initial overload of the registration system. The registration process is meanwhile well established. It will not be completed in the foreseeable future because new substances are constantly being added, but the huge number of registration applications is no longer being submitted. Annual growth of the list of registered substances has been between 1% and 2%, and between 4% and 5% for registration companies in recent years (see Table 3).

So, we can no longer talk about a system being overloaded, if polymers were included in the registration requirement. Against this background, one of the decisive arguments in 2006 for exempting polymers from the registration requirement no longer applies. Nevertheless, mandatory registration today would result in a considerable workload for industry, but also for the authorities. After all, there are more than 200 chemical types of common monomers,

and polymer combinations and mixtures are also being used more and more frequently. In a report prepared for the European Commission, experts estimate a total of between 70,000 and 400,000 polymer/plastic mixtures; exact figures are not available [25]. In addition, there are several thousand additives that would have to be evaluated in the field of polymer compounding [9]. This is a huge task. It will therefore be necessary to set priorities, proceed step by step, and answer the question of the purpose and **benefits of a mandatory registration**.

Table 3: REACH registrations and registered substances by companies from June 1, 2008 (EU27 + UK (Northern Ireland) + Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein); change compared to the previous year

Data as of	No. of Substances		Registrations ²⁵		No. of Companies		Source
30.09.2023	22,502		104,078		17,168		[62]
31.08.2024	22,786	+1.3%	107,372	+3.2%	17,829	+3.9%	[63]
31.01.2026	23,277	+2.2%	112,552	+4.8%	18,929	+6.2%	[64]

5.2. Health protection

Improving health protection has always been the guiding principle behind chemical legislation over the past 60 years (see above). The current situation regarding polymers and their significance for health protection is unclear, but this does not mean that there is no evidence of hazards and risks. On the contrary, science tells us: the risks are considered to be just as high as for non-polymers, which are already subject to registration and evaluation [25]. Furthermore, the current situation regarding additives (and NIAS or chemicals) in plastics is also unclear, as shown by a recently completed comprehensive EU research project [9] (see Figure 2 and Figure 4) and the particularly extensive body of data regarding Food Contact Materials (FCM) [8,43,65,66,67,68]. So, we have two problem areas that are relevant for registration under REACH: polymers and additives (and other chemicals in plastics). And both sectors will need to be addressed with equal priority. Ultimately, another argument in favour of treating them equally is that many of the properties of plastic products – which we will examine in more detail below – arise in the first place through the interaction of polymers with additives.

5.2.1. Polymers

Polymers fall through the screens of common hazard models. Following CLP Regulation [34], importers or manufacturers must classify and label polymers in accordance with defined

²⁵ "REACH covers different types of registrations: Full registrations (Art.10) and Intermediates (Art. 17&18). A substance can be registered for up to three registration types with one dossier. Therefore, the numbers ... do not add up to the total number of registrations. Furthermore, notifications made by companies under the previous chemicals' legislation (Directive 67/548/EEC – NONS Notifications) are considered registered under REACH. However, those NONS which were not claimed by any company by the deadline of 17/07/2022, were revoked by ECHA and they are not reported in these tables. NONS that were claimed, may be updated (ECHA has received a dossier submission under REACH) or not. ... NONS notifications which were claimed and updated are reported either under 'registered as full registration' or 'registered as intermediate'."

hazard criteria. A search for "polymer" in the C&L Inventory²⁶ (02.03.2026) yielded in sum only 15 substances, of them 13 with EC-number (five new and eight existing substances). This can probably be explained by the fact that the term 'polymer' does not necessarily have to be used for the substance name. We therefore assume that the proportion of polymers in the CLP database is underestimated.

With regard to polymers, the prevailing view to date has been that they are too large to be bioavailable, meaning that they cannot be absorbed by the body and therefore cannot cause any harm. This assessment needs to be considered carefully, as a distinction must be made between internal and external bioavailability. External bioavailability refers to reactions between polymers and surfaces (such as the skin, eyes or lungs of higher organisms), which can be quite serious (see below). For internal bioavailability, the molecule in question must, for example, be able to pass through cell membranes, which is not possible for very large molecules. However, there are certainly polymers on the market that are not so large and are capable of penetrating cells. Therefore, classification according to molecular size can be used to derive priorities for registration.

The highest internal bioavailability and therefore highest potential hazard or risks are likely to come from polymers smaller than 1000 Daltons (Da)²⁷. A medium risk would be between 1000 and 10,000 Da, and a low risk would be for polymers with a molecular weight of >10,000 Da. In 2020, in a report commissioned by the European Commission, Wood & PFA-Brussels [25] proposed that this classification be subject to mandatory registration within REACH for so-called "polymers requiring registration" (PRR), see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Polymers of low concern (PLC), polymers requiring registration (PRR) and other polymers (Da = Daltons) (own graph based on [25])

²⁶ ECHA CHEM: CLP Annex VI – harmonised classifications. <https://chem.echa.europa.eu/obligation-lists/clhList?pageIndex=1&pageSize=100>

²⁷ Dalton, abbreviated Da, is a term used in biochemistry to refer to the atomic mass unit. One Dalton is defined as one twelfth of the mass of the carbon isotope ¹²C. In polymers, it refers to the average molar mass of all monomer units that make up the polymer.

Following this proposal, "polymers of low concern" [69,70,71] should not be subject to registration. We, on the other hand, propose requiring notification with minimal requirements as regards the provision of data. Details on this matter were discussed in the CARACAL's (Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP)²⁸ Competent Authorities Sub-Group (CASG) on Polymers, a working group of Commission (lead), ECHA and member states, with industry representatives also taking part [72]. This also includes the question of how notification and registration can be simplified through a sensible group-based approach. The aim here is, on the one hand, to reduce the diversity of polymers mentioned above as far as possible and, on the other hand, to bring together the various stakeholders in the industry (joint submission) [73].

According to this, polymers with a molecular weight of less than 1000 Da should be subject to registration in the same way as non-polymers. For this group of cases, the submission of the registration dossier would then require the provision of data that enables a substance evaluation to be carried out. The substance evaluation would then determine whether the substance poses a real risk or hazard. This context makes it clear that the registration requirement proposed here, based on defined criteria, does not necessarily mean that the substances subject to registration ultimately pose actual hazards and risks. Criteria such as molecular size are merely a kind of trigger mechanism for a registration requirement (potential hazard or hazard alert).

Weber et al. [74] point out, that "the assumption that only molecules smaller than 1000 Daltons can be toxicologically relevant needs to be revisited because there is evidence that larger molecules can be absorbed in the intestinal gut tract, especially if so-called permeation enhancers are present [75]". Therefore, the group of >1000–10,000 Da should also be included at a later stage with lower priority. High-molecular-weight substances with a molecular weight of over 10,000 should only be subject to registration if they have defined chemical or physical properties (see below).

China is already further ahead in this regard, as – unlike in the EU – in principle **all** polymers have to be notified at minimum²⁹, bearing in mind the importance of the Inventory of Existing Chemical Substances in China (IECSC³⁰). Only those substances or polymers that are not listed in this register need to be registered (Ministry of Ecology and Environment (MEE) Order No.7, effective from 15.10.2010). Any substance not listed in IECSC is regarded as new chemical substance [76]. Under the current "Chinese REACH" (MEE Order No. 12, effective from 01.01.2021 [77]) new chemical substances are registered under three types: regular registration, simplified registration and record notification [78,79]. For polymers registration is required, as long as the polymer is defined as a new substance, even if all monomers are

²⁸ Competent Authorities for Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) (E02385). <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=2385>

²⁹ The criteria used for identifying polymers of low concern (PLC) in jurisdictions is handled differently by different countries, see OECD (2024), page 3. <https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/topics/policy-sub-issues/risk-management-risk-reduction-and-sustainable-chemistry/polymers-of-low-concern.pdf>

³⁰ Inventory of Existing Chemical Substances manufactured or imported in China.

listed in IECSC. Record notification – the lowest of the three levels – is mandatory for polymers under the conditions shown in Box 1.

Box 1: Prerequisite for record notification of polymers in China REACH

Record notification is mandatory for

1. "...
2. **Polymers** containing less than 2% monomers or reactants **which are new chemical substances, or polymers of low concern** (no volume limit), **including**
 - a) Polymer itself is not listed in the IECSC, but all the new monomers or reactants of the polymer are $\leq 2\%$ (w/w);
 - b) Polymer itself is not listed in the IECSC, but all the monomers or reactants of the polymer are listed in the IECSC;
 - c) The polymer's number-average molecular weight is between 1000 and 10,000 daltons. The content of oligomers in the polymer with molecular weight < 500 daltons is less than 10% (w/w) and the content of oligomers with molecular weight < 1000 daltons is less than 25% (w/w). **At the same time, the polymers must not contain functional groups of high concern or high reactivity;**
 - d) The polymer's number-average molecular weight is $\geq 10,000$ daltons. The content of oligomers in the polymer with molecular weight < 500 daltons is less than 2% (w/w), and the content of oligomers with molecular weight of < 1000 daltons is less than 5% (w/w);
 - e) Polyesters.

New chemical substances not conforming to the record registration conditions for polymers or meeting the exclusion requirements for polymers shall be subject to regular or simplified registration."

In sum, this means that notification of all polymers has been introduced in China and prioritisation for a registration according to molecular weight and defined chemical or physical properties, as we recommend, is being practised. In addition to molecular weight and bioavailability, high-molecular-weight substances $> 10,000$ Da should, as already mentioned, also be subject to registration if they possess certain properties that may pose a risk. This was also proposed by Wood et al. [25] (see Figure 3). In the past, it was assumed that polymers do not exhibit reactivity. Here, too, lessons have been learned, as shown by the following selection of polymers which can have hazardous properties³¹, which is why we are proposing a registration requirement for them:

- cationic polymers,
- anionic polymers,
- amphoteric polymers,
- polymers containing high levels of monomers or of low molecular weight oligomers,
- polymers with reactive functional groups; e.g. grafted polymers like compatibilizers³² for mechanical recycling [80,81,82,83] (see 8 Annex: Compatibilizers),

³¹ We have taken up the proposal by Wood & PFA-Brussels [25] and expanded it to include the aspects of 'persistence' and 'degradability'.

³² "A compatibilizer is an additive used to improve the interfacial adhesion between two immiscible or partially miscible polymers in a physical mixture (blending). By optimizing the dispersion of the blend morphology in a

- biodegradable or highly stable (persistent) polymers,
- water-soluble polymers.

In some cases, the registration requirement is essentially based on the fact that, although certain high-molecular-weight polymers do not exhibit internal bioavailability, they can certainly have a damaging effect on surfaces (external bioavailability). So, the point is to look for possible chemical reactivity of the polymers or parts of the polymer, see proposal by Wood & PFA-Brussels [25]. Table 4, taken from ECETOC [84], shows a selection of reactive functional groups that play a role in polymer chemistry.

However, a registration requirement would also apply if polymers contained very high proportions of monomers or oligomers. These components exhibit internal bioavailability. There is a wide-ranging scientific debate regarding the hazards and risks posed by monomers in particular. One view is that the issue of monomers is underestimated and that it ranks among the most significant potential risks. For instance, a study shows that 30 of the detected contaminants in FCMs are monomers, 22 of which migrate into food [65]. This therefore demonstrates that monomers can indeed be relevant to human exposure, which, in our view, argues in favour of a registration requirement should defined limit values be exceeded.

It must also be borne in mind that polymers with a high degradability – which is certainly a desirable property for packaging plastics, for example [85] – will form metabolites that are bioavailable as they degrade. Whether these degradation products pose a hazard or a risk should be assessed as part of the registration process. We examine the concepts of 'marine protection' and persistence in detail in section 5.4. Finally, water-soluble polymers may pose aquatic hazards, which should also be investigated in more detail as part of the registration process.

As an interim conclusion, we therefore recommend mandatory registration for polymers where a low molecular weight suggests internal bioavailability. We also propose mandatory registration where higher-molecular-weight polymers exhibit defined chemical or physical properties.

more homogenous way with a compatibilizer, the performance of the compound increases by improving the mechanical properties." <https://thecompoundcompany.com/products/compatibilizers/>

Table 4: Definitions and examples for reactive functional groups (RFGs) of low, moderate and high concern [84]

Concern	Low	Moderate	High
Definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack reactivity, or low adverse reactivity in a biological setting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evidence for biological reactivity, but effects not sufficiently severe to be of high concern Sufficient evidence to establish that RFG is of moderate concern 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evidence for adverse effects in humans or conclusive evidence of severe effects in animals Where there is no, insufficient, or contradictory information on an RFG, it can be assigned as being of high concern until new evidence enable reappraisal
FGEW^a threshold^b	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No threshold 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Threshold for polymers of low concern: >1000 Da 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Threshold for polymers of low concern: >5000 Da
<p>In the USA, cut-off limits for combinations of functional groups have also been implemented, and it must be checked if more than one RFG is present in the polymer (Table 2 on p. 16 of US EPA, 1997).</p>			
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aliphatic hydroxyl Blocked isocyanates (including ketoxime blocked isocyanates) Butenedioic acid Carboxylic acid Conjugated olefinic groups (if contained in naturally-occurring fats, oil and carboxylic acids) Halogens (except reactive benzylic or allylic halides) Thiols Unconjugated nitrile Unconjugated olefinic considered ordinary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acid anhydrides Acid halides Aldehydes Alkoxysilanes bearing alkoxy-groups >C₂-alkoxysilanes Allyl ethers Conjugates olefinic groups (except those contained in naturally-occurring fats, oils and carboxylic acids) Cyanates Epoxides Hemiacetals Imines (ketimines and aldimines) Methylol-amides Methylol-amines Methylol-ureas Unsubstituted positions ortho and para to phenolic hydroxyl Canada Phase 2^c: Structural features, such as ethylene glycol, amines or maleic acid anhydrides, which may be associated with human health risks (e.g. skin sensitisation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alkoxysilanes with alkoxy of C1- or C2-alkoxysilanes Alpha lactones Amines Aziridines Beta lactones Carbodiimides Halosilanes Hydrazines Hydrosilanes (as per NICNAS in April 2019^b) Isocyanates Isothiocyanates Partially hydrolysed acrylamides Pendant acrylates Pendant methacrylates Vinyl sulfones or analogous compounds Other RFGs not in low or moderate concern groups

a FGEW = functional group equivalent weight

b As implemented in US EPA (1997); Canada (2005a, b); NICNAS (2019b, c). While the present Technical Report was being finalised in April 2019, NICNAS published expansions to the PLC criteria with immediate effect. Amongst other issues, the lists of moderate- and high-concern RFGs were aligned with those used in USA and Canada; <https://www.nicnas.gov.au/New-scheme-1-July-2020/Early-commencement-whats-already-changed-for-importers-and-manufacturers#criteria>. In this update of the PLC criteria, NICNAS further lists azo groups, disulfides, and trithiocarbonates as high-concern RFGs.

c Final Screening Assessment for the Second Phase of Polymer Rapid Screening (Canada, 2018b); see also <https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/evaluating-existing-substances/second-polymer-rapid-screening.html>

If one were to recommend the introduction of a notification and registration requirement for polymers in the EU, one would certainly be confronted with the ongoing discussion about a lack of competitiveness due to EU overregulation and imports of cheaper polymers from, e.g., China. However, this argument does not hold water given the legal situation in China. Table 5 shows the significant differences between China REACH and EU REACH, based on [77], with focus on polymers.

Table 5: Significant differences between China REACH and EU REACH, with focus on polymers, based on [77,78]

Aspect	China REACH (MEE Order No. 12)	EU REACH (Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006) [13]
Substance to be registered	Substance not listed in IECSC (= new substance), regardless its quantities manufactured in / imported into China	New substance manufactured and placed on the market in / imported into the EU / EEA (European Economic Area) ¹
Registration type / mass (Mg) per year and per applicant (company)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular registration: ≥ 10 Mg/a • Simplified registration: 1–10 Mg/a • Record notification: < 1 Mg/a OR defined polymers (see Box 1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard (Full) registration: ≥ 1 Mg/a • Reduced registration for intermediates (does not apply to monomers)
Registration of monomers	<i>See above</i>	Standard registration
Registration of polymers	Polymers are either already listed in IECSC or must be newly registered, as long as the polymer is defined as a new substance, even if all monomers are listed in IECSC.	Polymer itself is exempted from registration (and evaluation).
Requirements for record notification of polymers	List of monomers/reactants, plot of molecular weight distribution, mechanism of polymerisation, materials illustrating that substances in question are not polymers which are subject to regular or simplified registration	Polymer itself is exempted from registration.

¹ EU-27 plus Northern Ireland, Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway

Furthermore, comparable regulations are in force in other countries such as the USA [86,87], Canada [88], Australia [89,90], Japan [91], Taiwan [92], South Korea [93,94], and the Philippines [95,96]. Nor would the regulation we propose be new to the EU. Since 1993, a notification requirement similar in technical terms to our proposal has applied to new polymers (see Table 1). However, this was repealed when REACH came into force.

Now, the polymer regulation in China described in Table 5 does not mean that everything there has already been notified and registered, as the regulation dates from 2021 and is probably just getting started. Companies tell us that the relevant authorities have extensive powers to demand comprehensive evidence, even in the case of existing polymers. In

practice, however, this rarely happens. But if we were to look five to ten years into the future, we would have a situation where, for the first time in our more than 60-year history of chemical safety in the EU, China and other countries has overtaken us. This would mean that plastic imports from China would not only be cheaper, but also safer. Not a pleasant prospect.

5.2.2. Additives and other chemicals

And there is also cause for concern regarding the additives. Even if – as shown above – some of these substances are registered, we cannot rule out that their use as additives in polymers has not been covered in all cases by the registration and has therefore not been evaluated by the registrant. And moreover, according to the aforementioned EU project PlastChem [9], ≈3,650 substances would have to be examined more closely in terms of their hazardousness (PBMT – persistence, bioaccumulation, mobility, and toxicity) and substitutability (Figure 4). And FCM data also shows that over 300 substances should be phased out because of hazardousness [65] – a really high number.

Figure 4: Hazard information for chemicals used or detected in plastics according to polymer type (own graphic, according to [9])

But are additives relevant which are bound in the plastic? Many scientific studies in recent years have proven the assumption of being "bound" to be false³³. Depending on the known physical laws, the substances are more or less mobile, depending on the chemical environment of the polymer molecules and the properties of the additives, and they can also leave the plastic body by migration³⁴ [74,80,97,98,99,100]. At this point, polymers with lower

³³ Strictly speaking, this finding would not be so new if more attention had been paid to older studies on plasticisers and PVC.

³⁴ There are also additives that are covalently bonded to the polymer (flame retardants, for example). These additives do not migrate.

molecular weights or short chains will generally pose higher risks (because of higher migration). And the risk of migration/elution increases as the size of the plastic body decreases.³⁵ This plays a significant role in the case of microplastics and nanoplastics.

Indirect evidence, such as studies of human bodily fluids (blood, urine, breast milk, semen), also shows that plastic additives are detectable there. Biomonitoring in humans reveals high concentrations of plasticisers, bisphenols, UV filters, flame retardants, PFAS, and many more [101,102,103,104,105,106,107,108,109,110,111]. For FCM alone, 194 substances found in packaging were detected in humans, 80 of which are of high concern [43]. But what do these measurements mean? Does this affect our health? These questions have been the subject of intensive scientific research parallel to 60 years of chemicals legislation.

Exposure occurs either through direct contact with plastic products, such as FCM / food, textiles or children's toys, or through indoor environments in homes and vehicles. In temperate climates, people spend around 90% of their lives indoors. Exposure occurs either through the air or through indoor dust. The analysis of vacuum cleaner dust is a good marker for these exposures [112,113,114,115,116]. Based on these findings, the focus of regulatory activities should be readjusted. Plastic additives are among the dominant exposures compared to other sources that have been the focus of attention in the past or to date, partly also due to the increase in plastic products in our living environment.

But what health risks are in the main focus here? Europe represents less than 10% of the world's population, but accounts for 25% of all cancer cases [117]³⁶. The risk of developing cancer before the age of 75 years (cumulative risk) for all sexes was 27.9% (31.9% for males and 24.7% for females) in 2022 [118]. In the EU, cancer is the second leading cause of mortality [117]. To this day, various additives must be mentioned as a cause in this context [119].

Other health effects (known as endpoints in technical terminology) are also under discussion. Bisphenols, for example, have been linked to cardiovascular disease and obesity [119].

People are wondering where the increasing diagnoses of "abnormalities" in children (attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), delayed language development etc.) come from. Is this a 'fashion trend'? Scientific findings point in a different direction, suggesting a chemical explanation: plasticisers have hormone-like effects and their concentrations in human matrices correlate with medical diagnoses [120,121,122,123]. It should be noted that, for these effects, the total amount of pollutants must be considered as a mixture (bisphenols, plasticisers, PFAS, etc.) to which people are exposed (multisubstance exposure) [124]. Fortunately, some of these plasticisers, such as DEHP, have since been banned. And the concentrations in blood or urine in recent studies have also shown a decrease of these "legacy" additives. However, the fact that we are still detecting measurable concentrations in human matrices certainly has a lot to do with the fact that imported products still contain these substances. We are also finding that the concentration of substitutes here is increasing.

³⁵ For this reason, elution tests are usually carried out on finely ground material.

³⁶ This is certainly also attributable in part to improved diagnostics in the EU.

But whether these substitutes are safe for use must be ensured as part of the registration and evaluation procedures under REACH.

We must also address the limited significance of human biomonitoring, as only a very small selection of pollutants and plastic additives are examined in comparison with the wide variety of substances described above. Not all of the more than 10,000 or $\approx 3,650$ substances are equally important, if only in terms of the quantities used. It is also possible that some substances fall below the 1 Mg-limit for registration. However, we do not know this at present, partly because the registration requirement does not apply; otherwise, such figures would have to be provided. And human biomonitoring can only examine a selection of substances, if only for cost reasons. To make matters more difficult, sufficiently sensitive detection methods for blood or urine have been developed for only a few of these additives. This means that even with a very large budget for human biomonitoring, only those substances for which detection methods exist can be examined. The availability of a suitable detection method in blood, urine or other human samples could also be a requirement under the registration process. Such detection methods should in particular be available for additives used in consumer products in significant quantities.

As a further interim conclusion, the current mid-term review of the EU's 'Zero Pollution' action plan can be cited: "Mixtures of pollutants including emerging ones, such as endocrine disruptors and pharmaceuticals, are becoming an increasing concern. Human biomonitoring is showing examples of effects of multiple chemicals on human health and some reports show that the effects of exposure to certain chemicals can have significant health costs. At the same time, these data show that effective regulation reduces the exposure and can lead to measurable improvements within short time frames" [125].

5.2.3. Proposals for legislative action in the field of health protection

The European Commission's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability [22] provides the framework for our regulatory proposals relating to health protection. It states: "The Commission will ... extend the generic approach to risk management to ensure that consumer products – including, among other things, food contact materials, toys, childcare articles, cosmetics, detergents, furniture and textiles – do not contain chemicals that cause cancers, gene mutations, affect the reproductive or the endocrine system, or are persistent and bioaccumulative."

The studies commissioned by the Commission in preparation for the introduction of a mandatory registration call for a strict separation of polymers (including stabilisers, starters, etc.) and additives. Only polymers are proposed for inclusion in REACH registration. Other scientific studies emphasize the unity of polymers and additives and see a common need for combined action in this area [9].

There are good arguments for both perspectives. Separate registration of polymers and additives has the advantage of simplifying political decision-making by making it clearer. Furthermore, mixtures would have to be registered, which would essentially amount to a kind of "product registration". This is outside the REACH regulation. In current substance law

this approach (authorisation of products) is used for plant protection products and biocides. However, this is done for a much more manageable number of cases and with a much more in-depth assessment by the authorities. The major disadvantage of separation is that the connection between additives and polymers is lost when creating the registration dossiers.

Based on the arguments outlined above, we recommend following the Commission's approach and treating additives and polymers separately. With regard to additives, legislators could take the position that, for health protection reasons, it is not permissible to use **unregistered** substances as additives, especially for applications that are contact-sensitive. The scientific findings of recent years mentioned above could be cited as additional justification. The ECHA database currently contains just under 23,300 registered substances. According to [9], of the 16,352 chemicals found in plastics, around 10,345 cannot be evaluated (grey list). If they were registered, they could be evaluated. We must therefore assume that there is a high number of unreported cases of additive use, as suggested by the literature from the FCM sector cited above.

In Europe, registration should, as part of the parallel introduction of the registration requirement for polymers, also require that the dossiers cover the use of additives in plastic products. In addition, it should be stated whether the additives are used in products that come into close contact with consumers (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Recommendation for subsequent testing and regulating polymer additives

The scientific community has proposed that leachate tests in particular be carried out to detect toxic migration [9].

A transition period could be granted for the subsequent registration of additives (>1 Mg/a). Furthermore, this regulation could then be implemented in stages depending on the intensity of contact between the plastic products and consumers or users (Figure 5).

As already stated, the focus of registration and subsequent evaluation would be on consumer goods (contact sensitivity). The ECHA's task would then be to subject this assessment to a technical review (double check). The areas of priority evaluation would be addressed sequentially in the ECHA's Community Rolling Action Plan (CoRAP) [126].

There are well-founded exceptions to the registration requirement in individual cases. These can certainly be retained. But these are only a few isolated cases. In the EU's positive list for packaging plastics, 867 of the 1078 unique substances/entries listed are used as additives or polymer processing aids (PPAs). Of them, 245 don't have an EC-number, i.e. are not registered under REACH. Three of them are a "confidential or not yet assessed substance" [127]. Regarding all entries, the result is the same. Nearly 30% of all substances/entries listed here (304 of 1078) are not registered. Studies show that, despite this list being legally

binding, many substances appear in food contact materials (FCMs) that are not included on this list [99,128]. Nevertheless, we conclude that the idea of achieving greater safety through a positive list for food contact materials is a good one. However, it would need to be much more strictly enforced. Only additives included on this list should be permitted. Other additives would then be prohibited and would render a product unmarketable on the EU market. Furthermore, as demonstrated, the existing positive list would also need to be revised. A minimum requirement would be that, after a defined period, only registered additives appear on the positive list (including EC number). Unregistered additives should then be prohibited from the specified date. A positive list that would be desirable in the medium term should then contain only additives that have been registered and evaluated by the ECHA.

However, the obligation to use only registered substances cannot be standardised in REACH, but only in the respective product regulations (children's toys, FCM, textiles, electrical and electronic equipment (Restriction of Hazardous Substances, RoHS), etc.).

We therefore propose that these areas of substance and product law be better harmonised, which is also recommended by other authors [129]. It would probably be sensible to introduce, alongside a positive list for FCM, further positive lists of a similar level of safety and binding force for other applications of plastics. Here, too, the focus should initially be limited to applications involving direct consumer contact. Only additives from these positive lists would then be permitted for these products. Only registered and evaluated substances are permitted on this list, which would have to be dealt with in substance legislation. POPs, SVHC substances and carcinogenic or mutagenic substances cannot be included in this positive list. As of December 2025, the database of the Baden-Württemberg State Agency for the Environment (LBUW) contains over 130 entries on SVHC substances, which are or may be used as additives in plastics [130]. Twenty SVHCs alone have been newly added in the last four years. See also ECHA's current action plan, which sets out its intention to assess several key additives against the SVHC criteria [49].

For the evaluation, the focus could again be on the following chemical groups, suggested from the scientific community [9]:

- Aromatic amines
- Aromatic aldehydes
- Alkylphenols
- Salicylate esters
- Aromatic ethers
- Bisphenols
- Phthalates
- Benzothiazoles
- Organometallics
- Parabens
- Azodyes
- Aceto/benzophenones
- Chlorinated paraffins
- Benzotriazole
- Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)

As an interim conclusion, furthermore, within approximately 15 years at the latest, only registered and evaluated substances should be permitted for use in plastics intended for contact-sensitive products. For imports, laboratory tests would then have to be submitted to confirm that only additives from the respective positive list were used.

5.3. Transparency for the circular economy – high quality recycling

Today, mechanical recycling is in crisis for many reasons. One reason is the so-called Risk Cycle, i.e., the problem of legacy additives that are banned in new plastic but, due to a time delay, end up via waste in recyclates [10,12]. This is a difficult grey area for recyclers and an image problem for economic success. Greater transparency could be helpful here.

5.3.1. The digital product passport (DPP)

The registration requirement provides data that would also be useful for high-quality recycling. With the new Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) [131], information on the substances of concern used, including their respective concentrations, is likely to be passed on in future throughout the product processing chain³⁷, right up to the recycling stage. The digital product passport (DPP)³⁸ is the key tool for this transfer of information. According to ESPR Article 7 (5), the DPP must contain at least (under others) "(e) information relevant for disassembly, preparation for reuse, reuse, recycling and the environmentally sound management of the product at end-of-life."

The digital product passport, which must be created in accordance with the regulations for children's toys [132], is a step in the same direction. The Commission's recent proposal to have the recycled materials produced tested in laboratories and to pass on the information to the supply chain [133,134] is also to be welcomed.

5.3.2. Proposals for legislative action in the area of circularity

All regulations governing the digital documentation of polymers, additives, and other chemicals should be harmonised into a uniform digital product passport. This provides recyclers with data to carry out high-quality recycling.

Exposure analysis must be carried out as part of the registration process. It will become apparent how substances leave the plastic matrix and what exposures will occur under which scenarios (leachate tests). These analyses are not available today partly because polymers are not subject to registration requirements.

5.4. Marine protection

5.4.1. Persistence in the open environment

When it comes to registration, individual polymers would definitely have to be classified as "persistent" (vP) if one follows the established rules on evaluating substances. But this is only a problem for polymers that end up in the environment in significant amounts as intended or are the main components of, say, marine litter. These polymers would then definitely be considered candidates for substitution. However, replacing PP with PS or PE, for example, would be of little benefit because the polymers all exhibit a similarly high persistence in the

³⁷ Unfortunately, it is still unclear what the regulations for intermediate products will look like.

³⁸ Respectively, the digital material passport (DMP)

aquatic environment. It would also not make sense to ban these polymers altogether, because their persistence as a building product is, for example, a basic prerequisite for their use.

5.4.2. Proposals for legislative action in the area of marine litter

However, biodegradable polymers would be a substitute alternative for the applications that account for the majority of marine pollution (selected packaging made of PE, PP, and PET, cigarette filters, etc.). For such a substitution, it will be necessary to involve the packaging and food industries. Companies that contribute significantly to marine litter and therefore have a keen interest in finding solutions are particularly well suited for this cooperation [135]. Of course, there is no single solution to the problem of marine litter. It also involves waste management, changes in awareness, and further education. But we must not rule out legislative activities that tackle the root of the problem, namely the high persistence (vP) of polymers for the products that make up the bulk of marine litter. At the very least, it would be worth a try.

Of course, these biodegradable polymers should not cause new problems. This would have to be ensured after registration in a thorough REACH procedure, as we recommended above. In this procedure, the requirements for packaging from a food safety perspective and for degradability in a marine environment would first have to be defined (third-generation biodegradable plastics [85,136]). Not an easy task.

Such biodegradable polymers would then need to be developed, a truly innovative task for experienced polymer chemists [85]. If this development were to succeed, substitutions could be specified and the vP polymers that are particularly relevant to marine litter could be restricted with defined transition periods. REACH has already been used as the legal basis for regulating, for example, emissions of primary microplastic particles (synthetic polymer particles) from cosmetics and much more (Annex XVII). Biodegradability or restrictions were prescribed as a solution (Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/2055) [137].

Secondary microplastics are formed through the breakdown (disintegration) of plastic products in the sea, partly due to wave motion³⁹. The degradability of polymers naturally leads to the formation of more fragments (microplastics), in contrast to polymers that are not degradable at all and can only be broken down mechanically. But the crucial difference is that these microplastic particles remain in the environment and are at most mechanically broken down. This creates a stockpile of microplastics that will gradually continue to grow. Only the biodegradability described above can completely prevent the continuous increase in the stock of secondary microplastics, because even the small particles would be biodegradable. Therefore, the legal requirement for a third generation of degradable plastics would also be the rapid biodegradability of the resulting fragments or microplastics. The biodegradability of microplastic particles would thus be regulated in the same REACH procedure through appropriate requirements and tests.

³⁹ Secondary microplastic particles are also produced by tyre abrasion and the washing of synthetic textiles. Other solutions must be found for these sources of microplastics.

As an interim conclusion, therefore, all relevant plastic packaging in the FCM sector – which accounts for the lion's share of litter – should be 'fully biodegradable', and targets to this effect should be set at EU level [129].

5.5. Economic interests

The interests of industry must also be taken into account in such far-reaching proposals. The advantage of REACH is that it can achieve substantial results that would also be economically viable. And the advantage of REACH for all parties involved is that the procedures are based on scientific principles. Furthermore, communication between the parties involved has become well-established and has proven its worth. The procedures ensure that no hasty decisions are made and that proportionate solutions are found in the end. In addition, economic and social aspects are also taken into account, including in a specialised committee (Committee for Socio-economic Analysis (SEAC)).

Of course, from an economic perspective, one might think that no registration requirement would be even better. However, it must also be taken into account that the need for action is so great that further activities under REACH, on a case-by-case basis, must be assumed. It then remains unclear whether the right priorities will always be set and proportionality maintained. Only the registration requirement for polymers and additives in the systematic but product-related and step-by-step approach proposed here provides certainty and predictability.

The preparatory discussions within the EU have also shown that the group approach and cooperation among registrants offer a good opportunity to reduce the burden on industry [72].

6. Conclusion – three regulatory proposals

The legal and factual arguments in favour of mandatory registration for polymers are presented. We classify the significance of the exemption for polymers from registration in a historical analysis of EU chemical regulation. Before REACH, new polymers were already regulated comparable to this, what we propose today. When REACH came into force, this provision was superseded by the exemption for polymers set out in the new regulation. This decision was a political compromise, based in part on the scientific assessments prevailing at the time regarding the low level of risk posed by polymers. We present the reasons for this special treatment of polymers and analyse how scientific progress has rendered these former justifications untenable today. We therefore conclude that this exemption is no longer justified today, both from a legal and a technical point of view.

We therefore propose, building on the European preparatory work by various scientists and bodies cited in this paper, a greatly simplified notification requirement for all polymers. The burden on industry and the authorities should be reduced through the creation of appropriate groups. Furthermore, we propose a mandatory registration requirement, accompanied by comprehensive dossiers, for polymers that may pose a risk.

However, when **introducing a registration requirement for polymers under REACH**, it should be limited to polymers or questions of concern, as otherwise the workload for industry and the authorities would become too high. Mandatory registration and evaluation of polymers will create economic benefits and outweighs the costs that would be incurred by the plastics industry [25]. **Therefore, based on the available studies, a first proposal is made as to what a registration requirement for polymers of concern could look like. In future, polymers with a low molecular weight (< 1000 Da) should be subject to registration in the same way as non-polymers. High-molecular-weight polymers should only be subject to registration if they possess defined chemical or physical properties that could pose a potential hazard. The criteria that trigger this registration requirement are described in more detail.** Our proposal overlaps somewhat with the relevant legislation in countries like the U.S., China and others.

The previous REACH-exemption of polymers from registration has led to an unclear situation regarding the additives used. According to our findings, only a subset of today's additives has been registered to date. In our opinion, **the use of additives in plastics** has not been sufficiently evaluated, which is ultimately also related to the exemption from the registration requirement for polymers. It is further shown that additives have become a dominant source of chemical emissions also due to the diversity of plastic products in people's living environment, which is also reflected in the results of human biomonitoring and human health effects.

A second regulatory proposal also serves to protect health. A systematic review of the relevant additives in the plastic matrix is recommended. A new regulation in product law could prohibit the use of unregistered additives with a transition period. This could be achieved by introducing positive lists for the manufacture of products in contact-sensitive areas. Only substances that are registered under REACH and have been evaluated by the dossier submitter will be included on this/these positive list or lists. After a specified period, all substances on the positive lists should also have been assessed by the relevant authorities, which would further enhance the list's reliability. Hazardous substances such as POPs, SVHCs or substances with carcinogenic or mutagenic properties are not included in this list. This will enable better integration of substance and product legislation. For imports, independent laboratory tests should be required to confirm compliance with the respective positive lists. This can be done by setting priorities based on the areas of application of contact-sensitive products (FCM/kitchen utensils, children's toys, textiles, indoor products).

A third regulatory proposal aims to improve environmental protection. A staggered registration requirement for very persistent polymers in specific products that are particularly relevant to marine litter, for example, could lead to substitution with less persistent, fully biodegradable plastics, which could also prevent the generation of secondary microplastics and nanoplastics. Of course, such an initiative would only be a partial contribution to solving the problem of, e.g., marine litter.

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8. Annex: Compatibilizers

Compatibilizers improve miscibility between immiscible or only poorly miscible polymer types to give a more homogeneous product. As a rule, they consist of small molecules with two different chemical regions, each of which is compatible with a certain polymer. They act as molecular anchors between these polymers (Fig. 1). They are effective for mixtures of two types of polymers, but not for heterogeneous mixtures. Compatibilizers that are suitable for all plastic combinations are not known.

Fig. 1: Compatibilization of polymers

(Graph based on <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=58277078>)

Following Ragaert et al. (2017) [1], "three main compatibilizer groups can be distinguished based on the interactions between the compatibilizer and the blend:

- **Block or graft copolymers:** these compatibilizers are built out of different polymer segments, and one of the polymer segment will be more compatible with the matrix phase and the other one with the dispersed phase. The compatibilizer will migrate towards the interface and reduce the interfacial tension. An example of this type is a block copolymer of PE and PP, used in mixed PE/PP blends.
- **Non-reactive polymers containing polar groups:** the interfacial tension is reduced by the secondary intermolecular interactions between these polymers. The non-reactive polymer will be compatible with the matrix. The compatibilization will be influenced by the type of secondary interaction (Van der Waals < dipoles < hydrogen bonding). PMMA and polycaprolactone (PCL) are example of this type of compatibilizers.
- **Reactive functionalized polymers:** the reactive group will covalently bond to the dispersed phase and the polymer backbone is compatible with the matrix. The adhesion between phases will be the highest for these types. Examples of this type of compatibilizer are PP grafted with maleic anhydride (PP-g-MA) or PP grafted with glycidyl methacrylate (PP-g-GMA)."

Tab. 1 gives a survey on commonly used compatibilizers for different polymeric systems by Ragaert et al. (2017 [1]).

Tab. 1: Commonly used compatibilizers for different polymeric systems [1]

Polymeric system	Commonly used compatibilizers (g = grafted with)	References (by [1])
PE–PET	PE-g-AA, PE-g-IA, PE-g-GMA, SEBS, SEBS-g-GMA, SEBS-g-MA	[2,3,4,5,6,7]
PP–PET	PP-g-AA, PP-g-MA, SEBS, SEBS-g-MA, SEBS-g-GMA, EVA, EVA-g-MA	[4,8,9,10,11,12,13]
PP–PE	EVA, EPDM, SEBS	[4,14,15,16]
PP–PA	PP-g-GMA, PP-g-MA, SEBS-g-MA	[4,17,18]
PE–PA	PE-g-MA, PE-g-GMA	[19,20,21,22]
PP–PS	SBS, SEBS, EVA	[23,24]
ABS–PC	ABS-g-MA, PP-g-MA, epoxy resins, PMMA	[25,26,27,28]
PC–PS	PC-g-PS, PS-PAR, SEBS-g-PC	[29,30,31]

AA	Acrylic acid	PC	Polycarbonate
ABS	Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene	PE	Polyethylene
EPDM	Ethylene propylene diene monomer	PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
EVA	Ethylene-vinyl acetate	PMMA	Polymethylmethacrylate
GMA	Glycidyl methacrylate	PS	Polystyrene
IA	Iodoacetyl	SBS	Styrene-butadiene-styrene copolymer
MA	Maleic anhydride	SEBS	Styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene copolymer
PA	Polyamide		
PAR	Polyarylate		

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